

Atomic Appends: Selling Cars and Coordinating Armies with Multiple Distributed Ledgers

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Abstract

The various applications using Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) or blockchains, have led to the introduction of a new “marketplace” where multiple types of digital assets may be exchanged. As each blockchain is designed to support specific types of assets and transactions, and no blockchain will prevail, the need to perform *interblockchain* transactions is already pressing.

In this work we examine the fundamental problem of interoperable and interconnected blockchains. In particular, we begin by introducing the *Multi-Distributed Ledger Objects* (MDLO), which is the result of aggregating multiple *Distributed Ledger Objects* – DLO (a DLO is a formalization of the blockchain) and that supports append and get operations of records (e.g., transactions) in them from multiple clients concurrently. Next we define the *AtomicAppends* problem, which emerges when the exchange of digital assets between multiple clients may involve appending records in more than one DLO. Specifically, AtomicAppend requires that either *all* records will be appended on the involved DLOs or *none*. We examine the solvability of this problem assuming *rational and risk-averse* clients that may *fail by crashing*, and under different client *utility* and *append* models, *timing models*, and client *failure scenarios*. We show that for some cases the existence of an intermediary is *necessary* for the problem solution. We propose the implementation of such intermediary over a specialized blockchain, we term *Smart DLO* (SDLO), and we show how this can be used to solve the AtomicAppends problem even in an asynchronous, client competitive environment, where all the clients may crash.

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1 Introduction

Blockchain systems, cryptocurrencies, and distributed ledger technology (DLT) in general, are becoming very popular and are expected to have a high impact in multiple aspects of our everyday life. In fact, there is a growing number of applications that use DLT to support their operations [26]. However, there are many different blockchain systems, and new ones are proposed almost everyday. Hence, it is extremely unlikely that one single DLT or blockchain

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45 system will prevail. This is forcing the DLT community to accept that it is inevitable to
 46 come up with ways to make blockchains interconnect and interoperate.

47 The work in [7] proposed a formal definition of a reliable concurrent object, termed
 48 Distributed Ledger Object (DLO), which tries to convey the essential elements of blockchains.
 49 In particular, a DLO is a sequence of records, and has only two operations, `append` and `get`.
 50 The `append` operation is used to attach a new record at the end of the sequence, while the
 51 `get` operation returns the sequence.

52 In this work we initiate the study of systems formed by multiple DLOs that interact
 53 among each other. To do so, we define a basic problem involving two DLOs, that we call *the*
 54 *Atomic Append problem*. In this problem, two clients want to append new records in two
 55 DLOs, so that either both records are appended or none. The clients are assumed to be
 56 selfish, but rational and risk-averse [22], and may have different incentives for the different
 57 outcomes. Additionally, we assume that they may fail by crashing, which makes solving the
 58 problem more challenging. We observe that the problem cannot be solved in some system
 59 models and propose algorithms that solve it in others.

60 1.1 Related Work

61 The Atomic Append problem we describe above is very related to the multi-party fair
 62 exchange problem [8], in which several parties exchange commodities so that everyone gives
 63 an item away and receives an item in return. The proposed solutions for this problem rely on
 64 cryptographic techniques [18, 20] and are not designed for distributed ledgers. In this paper,
 65 as much as possible, we want to solve Atomic Appends on DLOs via their two operations
 66 `append` and `get`, without having to rely on cryptography or smart contracts.

67 Among the first problems identified involving the interconnection of blockchains was
 68 Atomic Cross-chain Swaps [13], which can also be seen as a version of the fair exchange
 69 problem. In this case, two or more users want to exchange assets (usually cryptocurrency) in
 70 multiple blockchains. This problem can be solved by using escrows, hashlocks and timelocks:
 71 all assets are put in escrow until a value x with a special hash $y = \text{hash}(x)$ is revealed or a
 72 certain time has passed. Only one of the users knows x , but as soon as she reveals it to claim
 73 her assets, everyone can use it to claim theirs. Observe that this solution assumes synchrony
 74 in the system, in the sense that timelocks assume that the time to claim an asset is bounded
 75 and known, and that timeouts can be used to detect crashes.

76 This technique was originally proposed in on-line fora for two users [1], and it has been
 77 specified, validated, adapted, and used [17, 21]. For instance, the Interledger system [11]
 78 will use a generalization of atomic swaps to transfer (and exchange) currency in a network
 79 of blockchains and connectors, allowing any client of the system to interact with any other
 80 client. The Lightning network [19, 23] also allows transfers between any two clients via a
 81 network of micro-payment channels using a generalized atomic swap. Both Interledger and
 82 Lightning route and create one-to-one transfer paths in their respective networks. Herlihy [13]
 83 has formalized and generalized atomic cross-chain swaps beyond one-to-one paths, and shows
 84 how multiple cross-chain swaps can be achieved if the transfers form a strongly connected
 85 directed graph. Herlihy proves that the best strategy, in Game Theoretic sense, for the users
 86 is to follow the proposed algorithm, and that someone that follows it will never end up worst
 87 than at the start.

88 Unlike in most blockchain systems, in Hyperledger Fabric [5, 6] it is possible to have
 89 transactions that span several blockchains (blockchains are called *channels* in Hyperledger
 90 Fabric). This allows solving the atomic cross-chain swap problem using a third trusted
 91 channel or a mechanism similar to a two-phase commit [6]. Additionally, these solutions

92 do not require synchrony from the system. The ability of channels to access each other's
93 state and interact is a very interesting feature of Hyperledger Fabric, very in line with the
94 techniques we assume from advanced distributed ledgers in this paper. Unfortunately, they
95 seem to be limited to the channels of a given Hyperledger Fabric deployment.

96 There are other blockchain systems under development that, like Hyperledger Fabric,
97 will allow interactions between the different chains, presumably with many more operations
98 than atomic swaps. Examples are Cosmos [2] or PolkaDot [4]. These systems will have their
99 own multi-chain technology, so only chains in a given deployment can initially interact, and
100 other blockchain will be connected via gateways. Another proposal for interconnection of
101 blockchains is Tradecoin [12], whose target is to interconnect all blockchains by means of
102 gateways, trying to reproduce the way Internet works. Since the gateways will be clients of
103 the blockchains, the functionality of the global interledger system will be limited by what
104 can be done from the edge of the blockchains (i.e., by the blockchains' clients).

105 The practical need of blockchain systems to access the outside world to retrieve data (e.g.,
106 exchange rates, bank account balances) has been solved with the use of *blockchain oracles*.
107 These are relatively reliable sources of data that can be used inside a blockchain, typically
108 in a smart contract. The weakest aspect of blockchain oracles is trust, since the outcome
109 or actions of a smart contract will be as reliable as the data provided by the oracle. As of
110 now, it seems there is no good solution for this trust problem, and blockchains have to rely
111 on oracle services like Oraclize [3].

112 1.2 Contributions

113 As mentioned above, in this paper we extend the study of the distributed ledger reliable
114 concurrent object DLO started in [7] to systems formed of several such objects. Hence, the
115 first contribution is the definition of the Multiple DLO (MDLO) system, as the aggregation of
116 several DLOs (in similar way as a Distributed Shared Memory is the aggregation of multiple
117 registers [25]). The second contribution is the definition of a simple basic problem in MDLO
118 systems: the *2-AtomicAppends problem*. In this problem, the objective is that two records
119 belonging to two different clients are appended to two different DLOs atomically. Hence,
120 either both records are appended or none is. Of course, this problem can be generalized in a
121 natural way to the *k-Atomic Appends problem*, involving k clients with k records and up to
122 k DLOs.

123 Another contribution, in our view, is the introduction of a crash-prone risk-averse rational
124 client model, which we believe is natural and practical, especially in the context of blockchains.
125 In this model, clients act selfishly trying to maximize their utility, but minimizing the risk
126 of reducing it. We consider that this behavior is not a failure, but the nature of the client,
127 and any algorithm proposed under this model (e.g., to solve the 2-AtomicAppends problem)
128 must guarantee that clients will follow it, because their utility will be maximized without
129 any risk. For a complete specification of the clients' rationality their utility function has to
130 be provided. Two utility models are proposed. In the *collaborative utility model*, both clients
131 want the records to be appended over any other alternative. In the *competitive utility model*
132 a client still wants both records appended, but she prefers that only the other client appends.
133 This client model is complemented with the possibility that clients can fail by crashing.

134 We explore hence the solvability of 2-AtomicAppends in MDLO systems in which the
135 DLOs are reliable but may be asynchronous, and the clients are rational but may fail by
136 crashing. The first results we present consider a system model in which clients do not crash,
137 and show that Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends can be solved even under asynchrony, while
138 Competitive 2-AtomicAppends cannot be solved. Then, we further study Collaborative

139 2-AtomicAppends if clients can crash. In the case that at most one of the two clients can
 140 crash, we show that, if each client must append its own record (what we call *no delegation*),
 141 Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends cannot be solved even under synchrony. This justifies
 142 exploring the possibility of *delegation*: any client can append any record, if she knows it. We
 143 show that in this case Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends can be solved, even if the system is
 144 asynchronous (termination is only guaranteed under synchrony, though). However, delegation
 145 is not enough if both clients can crash, even under synchrony. (See Table 2 for an overview.)

146 The negative results (for Competitive 2-AtomicAppends even without crash failures and
 147 for Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends with up to 2 crashes) justifies exploring alternatives
 148 to appending directly or delegating among clients. Hence, we propose the use of an entity,
 149 external to the clients, that coordinates the appends of the two records. In fact, this entity is
 150 a special DLO with some level of intelligence, which we hence call *Smart DLO* (SDLO). The
 151 SDLO is by design a reliable entity to which clients can delegate (via appending in the SDLO)
 152 the responsibility of appending their records to their respective DLOs when convenient. The
 153 SDLO hence collects all the records from the clients and appends them. Since the SDLO is
 154 reliable, all the appends will complete. If some record is missing, the SDLO issues no append,
 155 to guarantee the properties of the 2-AtomicAppends problem. Thus, the SDLO can be used
 156 to solve Competitive and Collaborative k -AtomicAppends even when all clients can crash.

157 We believe that SDLO opens the door to a new type of interconnection and interoperability
 158 among DLOs and blockchains. While the use of oracles to access external information in
 159 a smart contract (maybe from another blockchain) is widely known, we are not familiar
 160 with blockchain systems in which one blockchain (i.e., possibly a smart contract) issues
 161 transactions in another blockchain. We believe this is a concept worth to be explored further.

162 The rest of the paper is structured as follows. The next section describes the model used
 163 and defines the AtomicAppends problem. Section 3 explores the 2-AtomicAppends problem
 164 when clients cannot crash. Section 4 studies the 2-AtomicAppends problem when clients can
 165 crash but SDLOs are not used. Section 5 introduces the SDLO and shows how it solves the
 166 AtomicAppends problem. Finally, Section 6 presents conclusions and future work.

167 **2 Problem Statements and Model of Computation**

168 **2.1 Objects and Histories**

169 An object type T is defined over the domain of values that any object of type T may take,
 170 and the operations that any object of type T supports. An object O of type T is a *concurrent*
 171 *object* if it is a shared object accessed by multiple processes [24]. A *history* of operations on
 172 an object O , denoted by H_O , is the sequence of operations invoked on O . Each operation π
 173 contains an *invocation* and a matching *response* event. Therefore, a *history* is a sequence of
 174 invocation and response events, starting with an invocation. We say that an operation π
 175 is *complete* in a history H_O , if the history contains both the invocation and the *matching*
 176 response events of π . History H_O is *complete* if it only contains complete operations. History
 177 H_O is *well-formed* if no two invocation events that do not have a matching response event in
 178 H_O belong to the same process p . That is, each process p invokes one operation at a time.
 179 An object history H_O is *sequential*, if it contains a sequence of alternating invocation and
 180 matching response events, starting with an invocation and ending with a response. We say
 181 that an operation π_1 *happens before* an operation π_2 in a history H_O , denoted by $\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$,
 182 if the response event of π_1 appears before the invocation event of π_2 in H_O .

183 **The Ledger Object (LO).** A *ledger* \mathcal{L} (as defined in [7]) is a concurrent object that stores
 184 a totally ordered sequence $\mathcal{L}.S$ of *records* and supports two operations (available to any

process p): (i) $\mathcal{L}.\text{get}_p()$, and (ii) $\mathcal{L}.\text{append}_p(r)$. A *record* is a triple $r = \langle \tau, p, v \rangle$, where p is the identifier of the process that created record r , τ is a *unique* record identifier from a set \mathcal{T} , and v is the data of the record drawn from an alphabet Σ . We will use $r.p$ to denote the id of the process that created record r ; similarly we define $r.\tau$ and $r.v$. A process p invokes an $\mathcal{L}.\text{get}_p()$ operation to obtain the sequence $\mathcal{L}.S$ of records stored in the ledger object \mathcal{L} , and p invokes an $\mathcal{L}.\text{append}_p(r)$ operation to extend $\mathcal{L}.S$ with a new record r . Initially, the sequence $\mathcal{L}.S$ is empty.

► **Definition 1** (Sequential Specification of a LO [7]). *The sequential specification of a ledger \mathcal{L} over the sequential history $H_{\mathcal{L}}$ is defined as follows. The value of the sequence $\mathcal{L}.S$ of the ledger is initially the empty sequence. If at the invocation event of an operation π in $H_{\mathcal{L}}$ the value of the sequence in ledger \mathcal{L} is $\mathcal{L}.S = V$, then:*

1. if π is an $\mathcal{L}.\text{get}_p()$ operation, then the response event of π returns V , while the value of $\mathcal{L}.S$ does not change, and
2. if π is an $\mathcal{L}.\text{append}_p(r)$ operation (and $r \notin V$), then at the response event of π the value of the sequence in ledger \mathcal{L} is $\mathcal{L}.S = V \| r$ (where $\|$ is the concatenation operator).

In this paper we assume that ledgers are *idempotent*, therefore a record r appears only once in the ledger even when the same record r is appended to the ledger by multiple `append` operations (and hence the $r \notin V$ in the definition above).

2.2 Distributed Ledger Objects (DLO) and Multiple DLOs (MDLO)

Distributed Ledger Objects (DLO). A *Distributed Ledger Object (DLO)* \mathcal{DL} , is a concurrent LO that is *implemented* by (and possibly replicated among) a set \mathcal{S} of (possibly distinct and geographically dispersed) computing devices, we refer as *servers*. Like any LO, \mathcal{DL} supports the operations `get()` and `append()`. We refer to the processes that invoke the `get()` and `append()` operations on \mathcal{DL} as *clients*.

Each server $s \in \mathcal{S}$ may fail. Thus, the distribution and replication of \mathcal{DL} offers availability and survivability of the ledger in case a subset of servers fail. At the same time, the fact that multiple clients invoke `append()` and `get()` requests to different servers, raises the challenge of *consistency*: what is the latest value of the ledger when multiple clients access the ledger concurrently? The work in [7] defined three consistency semantics to explain the behavior of `append()` and `get()` operations when those are invoked concurrently by multiple clients on a single DLO. In particular, they defined *linearizable* [14, 16], *sequential* [15], and *eventual* [9] consistent DLOs. In this work we will focus on *linearizable* DLOs which according to [7] are defined as follows:

► **Definition 2** (Linearizable Distributed Ledger Object [7]). *A distributed ledger \mathcal{DL} is linearizable if, given any complete, well-formed history $H_{\mathcal{DL}}$, there exists a sequential permutation σ of the operations in $H_{\mathcal{DL}}$ such that:*

1. σ follows the sequential specification of a ledger object (Definition 1), and
2. for every pair of operations π_1, π_2 , if $\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$ in $H_{\mathcal{DL}}$, then π_1 appears before π_2 in σ .

Multiple DLOs (MDLO). A *Multi-Distributed Ledger Object MDL*, termed MDLO, consists of a collection D of (heterogeneous) DLOs and supports the following operations: (i) $\text{MDL}.\text{get}_p(\mathcal{DL})$, and (ii) $\text{MDL}.\text{append}_p(\mathcal{DL}, r)$. The `get` returns the sequence of records $\mathcal{DL}.S$, where $\mathcal{DL} \in D$. Similarly, the `append` operation appends the record r to the end of the sequence $\mathcal{DL}.S$, where $\mathcal{DL} \in D$. From the locality property of linearizability [14] it follows that a MDLO is linearizable, if it is composed of linearizable DLOs. More formally:

229 ► **Definition 3** (Linearizable Multi-Distributed Ledger Object). *A multi-distributed ledger*
 230 *MDL is linearizable if $\forall \mathcal{DL} \in D$, \mathcal{DL} is linearizable, where D is the set of DLOs MDL*
 231 *contains.*

232 For the rest of this paper, unless otherwise stated, we will focus on MDLOs consisting
 233 of two DLOs. The same techniques can be generalized in MDLOs with more than two
 234 DLOs. In particular, we consider the records of two clients, A and B , on two different
 235 DLOs. For convenience we use DLO_X to denote the DLO appended by records from X , for
 236 $X \in \{A, B\}$. Similarly we denote as r_X the record that $X \in \{A, B\}$ wants to append on
 237 DLO_X . Furthermore, we view the DLOs and MDLOs as black boxes that reliably implement
 238 the specified service, without going into further implementation details.

239 2.3 AtomicAppends: Problem Definition

240 Multi-DLOs allow clients to interact with different DLOs concurrently. This is safe when the
 241 records involved in concurrent operations are independent. However, it may raise semantic
 242 consistency issues when there exists inter-dependent records, e.g. a record r_A must be
 243 inserted in DLO_A when a record r_B is inserted in DLO_B and vice versa. More formally, we
 244 say that a record r *depends* on a record r' , if r may be appended on its intended DLO, say
 245 \mathcal{DL} , only if r' is appended on a DLO, say \mathcal{DL}' . Two records, r and r' , are *mutually dependent*,
 246 if r depends on r' and r' depends on r . In this section we define a new problem, we term
 247 *AtomicAppends*, that captures the properties we need to satisfy when multiple operations
 248 attempt to append dependent records on different DLOs.

249 ► **Definition 4** (2-AtomicAppends). *Consider two clients, A and B , with mutually dependent*
 250 *records r_A and r_B . We say that records r_A and r_B are appended atomically on DLO_A and*
 251 *DLO_B respectively, when:*

- 252 ■ *Either both or none of the records are appended to their respective DLOs (safety)*
- 253 ■ *If neither A nor B fail, then both records are appended eventually (liveness).*

254 An algorithm *solves* the 2-AtomicAppends problem under a given system model, if it
 255 guarantees the safety and liveness properties of Definition 4.

256 The k -AtomicAppends problem, for $k \geq 2$, is a generalization of the 2-AtomicAppends
 257 that can be defined in the natural way (k clients, with k records, to be appended to up to k
 258 DLOs.) From this point onwards, we will focus on the 2-AtomicAppends problem, and when
 259 clear from the context, we will refer to it simply as *AtomicAppends*.

260 2.4 Communication, Timing and Append Models

261 The previous subsections are independent of the communication medium, and the failure and
 262 timing model. We now specify the communication and timing assumptions considered in
 263 the remainder of the paper. We also consider different models on who can append a specific
 264 record.

265 **Communication model:** We assume a *message-passing* system where messages are neither
 266 lost nor corrupted in transit. This applies to both the communication among clients and
 267 between clients and DLOs (i.e, the invocation and response messages of the operations).

268 **Timing models:** We consider *synchronous* and *asynchronous* systems with respect to both
 269 computation and communication. In the former, the evolution of the system is governed by a
 270 global clock and a local computation, a message delivery or a DLO operation is guaranteed to

271 complete within a predefined time-frame. For simplicity, we set this time-frame to correspond
 272 to one unit of time. In the latter, no timing assumptions are made beyond that they will
 273 complete in a finite time.

274 **Append models:** We consider three different append models. In the first, and most
 275 restrictive one, which we refer to as *Client appends with no delegation*, or **NoDelegation** for
 276 short, the only way a client can append its record, is by issuing append operations directly
 277 to the corresponding DLOs, i.e., no other entity, including the other client, can do so. The
 278 second one, referred to as *Client appends with delegation*, or **WithDelegation** for short, is a
 279 relaxation of the first model, in which one client can append the record of the other client (if
 280 it knows it). Finally, in the third model, a record can be appended by an external (w.r.t.
 281 the clients) entity, provided it knows the record.

282 2.5 Client Model and Utility-based Problem Definitions

283 2.5.1 Client Setting

284 We assume that clients are *rational*, i.e., they act selfishly, in a game-theoretic sense, in
 285 order to increase their utility [22]. Furthermore, clients are *risk-averse*, i.e., when uncertain,
 286 they prefer to lower the uncertainty, even if this might lower their potential utility [22]; we
 287 consider a client to be uncertain when her actions may lead to multiple possible outcomes.
 288 To this respect, a rational, risk-averse client runs its own utility-driven protocol that defines
 289 its strategy towards a given protocol (game), in such a way that it would not decrease its
 290 utility or increase its uncertainty.

291 Regarding failures, the only type of failure we consider in this work, is *crash failure*, in
 292 which a client might cease operating without any a priori warning.

293 Under this client model, *an algorithm A solves the AtomicAppends problem*, if
 294 it provides enough incentive to the clients to follow this algorithm (which guarantees the
 295 safety and liveness properties of Definition 4, possibly in the presence of crashes), without
 296 any client deviating from its utility-driven protocol. If no such algorithm can be designed,
 297 then *the AtomicAppends problem cannot be solved*.

298 2.5.2 Utility Models

299 Looking at the definition of the AtomicAppends problem, one might wonder what is the
 300 incentive of the clients to achieve this both-or-none principle on the appends. Let U_X denote
 301 the utility function (or incentive) for each client X . A selfish rational client X will try to
 302 maximize her utility U_X . Depending on the possible combinations of values the clients' utility
 303 functions can take, we can identify a number of different scenarios, we refer as *utility models*.
 304 Let us now motivate and specify two such utility models.

305 **Collaborative utility model.** Consider two clients A and B that have agreed to acquire
 306 a property (e.g., a piece of land) in common, and each has to provide half of the cost. If one
 307 of them, say A , pays while B backs off from the deal, then A incurs in expenses while not
 308 getting the property. On the other hand, B loses no money in this case, but her reputation
 309 may suffer. If both of them back off, they do not have any cost, while if both proceed with
 310 the payments then they get the property, which they prefer.

If $U_X()$ denotes the utility of agent $X \in \{A, B\}$, then we have the following relations in
 the scenario described:

$$U_X(\text{both agents pay}) > U_X(\text{no agent pays}) > U_X(\text{only agent } \bar{X} \text{ pays}) > U_X(\text{only agent } X \text{ pays}).$$

Utility model	Utility of client X
Collaborative	$U_X(\text{both append}) > U_X(\text{none appends}) > U_X(\text{only } \bar{X} \text{ appends}) > U_X(\text{only } X \text{ appends})$
Competitive	$U_X(\text{only } \bar{X} \text{ appends}) > U_X(\text{both append}) > U_X(\text{none appends}) > U_X(\text{only } X \text{ appends})$

■ **Table 1** The utility of client $X \in \{A, B\}$ in the two utility models considered.

311 In relation to the AtomicAppends problem, record r_A contains the transaction by which
 312 client A pays her share of the deal, and the append of r_A in DLO_A carries out this payment.
 313 Similarly for client B . So, here we see that under the above utility model, both clients
 314 have incentive for both appends to take place. Observe that this situation is similar to the
 315 *Coordinated Attack* problem [10], in which two armies need to agree on attacking a common
 316 enemy. If both attack, then they win; if only one of them attacks, then that army is destroyed,
 317 while the other is disgraced; if none of them attack, then the status quo is preserved.

318 These utility examples fall in the general utility model depicted in the first row of Table 1,
 319 which we call *collaborative*. We will be referring to the AtomicAppends problem under this
 320 utility model as the ***Collaborative AtomicAppends*** problem.

321 **Competitive utility model.** We now consider a different utility model. Consider two
 322 clients A and B that have agreed to exchange their goods. E.g, A gives his car to B , and
 323 B gives a specific amount as payment to A . If one of them, say A , gives the car to B , but
 324 B does not pay, then A loses the car while not getting any money. On the other hand, B
 325 gets the car for free! If both of them back off from the deal, then they do not have any cost.
 326 Both proceeding with the exchange is not necessarily their highest preference (unlike in the
 327 previous collaborative model).

So, if $U_X()$ denotes the utility of agent $X \in \{A, B\}$, then we have the following relations
 in the scenario described:

$$U_X(\text{only } \bar{X} \text{ proceeds}) > U_X(\text{both agents proceed}) > U_X(\text{no agent proceeds}) > U_X(\text{only } X \text{ proc.}).$$

328 In relation to the AtomicAppends problem, record r_A contains the transaction transferring
 329 the deed of A 's car to B , and the append of r_A in DLO_A carries out this transfer. Similarly,
 330 r_B contains the transaction by which client B transfers a specific monetary amount to A
 331 (pays for the car), and the append of r_B in DLO_B carries out this monetary transfer. Observe
 332 that this scenario is similar to the *Atomic Swaps* problem [13].

333 These utility examples fall in the general utility model depicted in the second row of
 334 Table 1, which we call *competitive*. We will be referring to the AtomicAppends problem
 335 under this utility model as the ***Competitive AtomicAppends*** problem.

336 No matter of the utility, failure or timing model assumed, our objective is to provide
 337 a solution to the AtomicAppends problem. Our investigation will focus on identifying the
 338 modeling conditions under which this is possible or not, and what is the impact of the model
 339 on the solvability of the problem.

3 AtomicAppends in the Absence of Client Crashes

341 We begin our investigation in a setting with no client crashes, so to study the impact of the
 342 utility model on the solvability of the problem.

343 It is not difficult to observe that in the absence of crash failures, even under asynchrony
 344 and NoDelegation, there is a straightforward algorithmic solution to the *Collaborative*

345 *AtomicAppends* problem: the algorithm simply has client A (resp. client B) issuing operation
 346 $append(DLO_A, r_A)$ (resp. $append(DLO_B, r_B)$). Based on Table 1, the clients' utilities are
 347 maximized when both append their corresponding records. Since there are no failures and
 348 the DLOs are reliable, these operation are guaranteed to complete, nullifying the clients'
 349 uncertainty. Hence, the clients will follow the algorithm, without deviating from their
 350 utility-driven protocol. This yields the following result:

351 ► **Theorem 5.** *Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends can be solved in the absence of failures, even*
 352 *under asynchrony and NoDelegation.*

353 However, this is *not* the case for the *Competitive AtomicAppends* problem. The problem
 354 cannot be solved, even in the absence of failures, in synchrony, and WithDelegation:

355 ► **Theorem 6.** *Competitive 2-AtomicAppends cannot be solved in the absence of failures,*
 356 *even in synchrony and WithDelegation.*

357 **Proof.** Let us firstly show that client A will never send its record r_A to the other client B .
 358 The reason is that this would carry a large risk of B appending r_A itself (and A is risk-averse).
 359 Observe that, independently on whether B already appended r_B or not, this would reduce
 360 A 's utility (see Table 1). Then, we secondly claim that client A will not directly append
 361 its own record r_A either. The reason is that, again, independently on whether B already
 362 appended r_B or not, this would reduce A 's utility (see Table 1). Hence, client A will not
 363 have its record r_A appended to DLO_A ever. However, this violates the liveness property of
 364 Definition 4, since by assumption neither A nor B fail by crashing. ◀

365 Note that the above result does not contradict the known solutions for atomic swaps
 366 (e.g., [13]), as the primitives used are stronger than the ones offered by DLO (e.g., some form
 367 of validation is needed for hashlocks). As we show in Section 5, the problem can be solved in
 368 the model we consider, if a reliable external entity is used between the clients and the MDLO.
 369 In view of Theorems 5 and 6, in the next section we focus on the study of *Collaborative*
 370 *AtomicAppends* in the presence of crash failures.

371 4 Crash-prone Collaborative AtomicAppends with Client Appends

372 In this section we focus on the Collaborative AtomicAppend problem assuming that at least
 373 one client may crash, under the NoDelegation and WithDelegation client append models.
 374 Observe from Table 1 that both clients have incentive to get both records appended, versus
 375 the case of no record appended, with respect to utilities. However, as we will see, in some
 376 cases, crashes introduce uncertainty that renders the problem unsolvable.

377 4.1 Client Appends with No Delegation

378 We prove that *Collaborative AtomicAppends* cannot be guaranteed by any algorithm \mathcal{A} , even
 379 in a *synchronous system*, when at least one client crashes and the clients cannot delegate the
 380 append of their records.

381 ► **Theorem 7.** *When at least one client crashes, Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends cannot be*
 382 *solved in the NoDelegation append model, even in a synchronous system.*

383 **Proof.** Consider an algorithm \mathcal{A} that clients can execute without deviating from their utility-
 384 driven protocol. Assume algorithm \mathcal{A} solves the Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends problem in
 385 the model described. Let E be an execution of algorithm \mathcal{A} in which no client crashes. By

386 liveness, both clients A and B must issue append operations. Consider the first client, say A
 387 without loss of generality, that issues the append operation. Let us assume that A issues
 388 $append(DLO_A, r_A)$ at time t . Hence, B issues $append(DLO_B, r_B)$ at time no earlier than t ,
 389 and A cannot verify that the record r_B is in the corresponding DLO_B until time $t' > t$.

390 Now consider execution E' of algorithm \mathcal{A} that is identical to E , up to time t . Now at time
 391 t client B crashes, and hence it never issues $append(DLO_B, r_B)$. Since A cannot differentiate
 392 until time t this execution from E , it issues $append(DLO_A, r_A)$ at time t , appending r_A
 393 to DLO_A . Even if after time t , A detects the crash of client B , by the specification of
 394 NoDelegation, it cannot append record r_B in DLO_B . This, together with the fact that B
 395 has crashed, yields that record r_B is never appended to DLO_B , violating safety. Hence, we
 396 reach a contradiction, and algorithm \mathcal{A} does not solve the Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends
 397 problem. ◀

398 4.2 Client Appends With Delegation

399 Let us now consider the more relaxed client append model of WithDelegation. It is not
 400 difficult to see that in this model, the impossibility proof of Theorem 7 breaks. In fact, it
 401 is easy to design an algorithm that solves the collaborative AtomicAppends problem in a
 402 synchronous system, if at most one client crashes. In a nutshell, first both clients exchange
 403 their records. When a client has both records, it appends them (one after the other) to the
 404 corresponding DLO; otherwise it does not append any record. We refer to this algorithm as
 405 Algorithm \mathcal{A}_{DSync} and its pseudocode is given as Code 1. We show:

406 ▶ **Theorem 8.** *In the WithDelegation append model, Algorithm \mathcal{A}_{DSync} solves the Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends problem in a synchronous system, if at most one client crashes.*

408 **Proof.** If no client crashes, then the proof of the claim is straightforward. Hence, let us
 409 consider the case that one client crashes, say A . There are three cases:

- 410 (a) Client A crashes before sending its record. In this case, client B will not append any
 411 record and the problem is solved (none case).
- 412 (b) Client A crashes after sending its record, but before it does any append. In this case
 413 client B will receive A 's record and append both records (both case).
- 414 (c) Client A crashes after it performs one or two of the appends. Client B will perform
 415 both appends, and since DLOs guarantee that a record is appended only once (they are
 416 idempotent), the problem is solved (both case).

417 The above cases and Table 1 suggest that the clients have no risk in running Algorithm
 418 \mathcal{A}_{DSync} with respect to their utility-driven protocol. Hence, the claim follows. ◀

419 We note that algorithm \mathcal{A}_{DSync} solves the problem also in the asynchronous setting,
 420 without of course being able to implement the "else" statement (line 5), since in asynchrony,
 421 a client cannot distinguish the case on whether the other client has crashed or its message is
 422 taking too long to arrive. To this respect, we slightly modify the description of the algorithm
 423 to better highlight the inability to detect crashes. We refer to this version of the algorithm
 424 as \mathcal{A}_{DAsync} ; its pseudocode is given as Code 2. We show:

425 ▶ **Theorem 9.** *In the WithDelegation append model, Algorithm \mathcal{A}_{DAsync} solves the Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends problem in an asynchronous system, if at most one client crashes.*

427 **Proof.** As before, we will prove this by case analysis. If no client crashes, then the proof
 428 follows easily, given the fact that a DLOs guarantees that a record is appended only once.
 429 Hence, let us consider the case that one client crashes, say A . There are three cases:

Code 1 \mathcal{A}_{DSync} : AtomicAppends WithDelegation, Synchrony, at most one crash; code for Client $X \in \{A, B\}$.

```

1: send  $r_X$  to client  $\bar{X}$ 
2: If  $r_{\bar{X}}$  is received from client  $\bar{X}$  then
3:   append( $DLO_X, r_X$ )
4:   append( $DLO_{\bar{X}}, r_{\bar{X}}$ )
5: Else (client  $\bar{X}$  has crashed)
6:   no append

```

Code 2 \mathcal{A}_{DAsync} : AtomicAppends WithDelegation, Asynchrony, at most one crash; code for Client $X \in \{A, B\}$.

```

1: send  $r_X$  to client  $\bar{X}$ 
2: wait until  $r_{\bar{X}}$  is received from client  $\bar{X}$ 
3:   append( $DLO_X, r_X$ )
4:   append( $DLO_{\bar{X}}, r_{\bar{X}}$ )

```

- 430 (a) Client A crashes before sending its record. In this case, client B will not proceed to
431 append any record (none case). Observe that client B might not terminate, but the
432 problem (safety) is not violated.
- 433 (b) Client A crashes after sending its record, but before it does any append. In this case
434 client B will receive A 's record and append both records (both case).
- 435 (c) Client A crashes after it performs one or two of the appends (it means it has sent its
436 record to client B). Client B will perform both appends, and since DLOs guarantee that
437 a record is appended only once, the problem is solved (both case).

438 The above cases and Table 1 suggest that the clients have no risk in running Algorithm
439 \mathcal{A}_{DAsync} with respect to their utility-driven protocol. Hence, the claim follows. ◀

440 As already discussed in case (a) of the above proof, it is possible for the client that has
441 not crashed to wait forever, as it cannot distinguish the case when the message is taking
442 too long to arrive and the append operation is taking too long to complete, from the case
443 when the other client has crashed. Hence, algorithm \mathcal{A}_{DAsync} , under certain conditions, is
444 *non-terminating*¹.

445 Furthermore, it is not difficult to see that if both clients fail, neither algorithm \mathcal{A}_{DAsync}
446 nor algorithm \mathcal{A}_{DSync} can solve the Collaborative AtomicAppends problem. For example,
447 in the proof of Theorem 8, in case (b), client B could crash right after appending its own
448 record (i.e., r_B is appended, but r_A is not). This violates safety. In fact, we now show that
449 if both clients can crash, the problem is not solvable, even under synchrony.

450 ▶ **Theorem 10.** *When both clients can crash, the Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends problem*
451 *cannot be solved WithDelegation, even in a synchronous system.*

452 **Proof.** Consider an algorithm \mathcal{A} that clients can execute without deviating from their utility-
453 driven protocol. Assume algorithm \mathcal{A} solves the Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends problem in
454 the model described. Let E be an execution of algorithm \mathcal{A} in which no client crashes. By
455 liveness, both records r_A and r_B must be eventually appended. Consider the first record
456 appended, say r_A w.l.o.g., and the client that issued the append operation, say A w.l.o.g.. Let

¹ Hence, in practice this may force a client to use timeouts in order to avoid blocking forever.

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457 us assume that A issues $append(DLO_A, r_A)$ at time t . Hence, $append(DLO_B, r_B)$ is issued
458 at time no earlier than t , and A cannot verify that the record r_B is in the corresponding
459 DLO_B until time $t' > t$.

460 Now consider execution E' of algorithm \mathcal{A} that is identical to E , up to time t . Now at time
461 t client B crashes, and hence it never issues $append(DLO_B, r_B)$. Since A cannot differentiate
462 until time t this execution from E , it issues $append(DLO_A, r_A)$ at time t , appending r_A to
463 DLO_A . Then, at time $t+1$ (immediately after $append(DLO_A, r_A)$ completes) A also crashes,
464 and hence never issues $append(DLO_B, r_B)$. Since $append(DLO_B, r_B)$ is never issued, record
465 r_B is never appended to DLO_B , violating safety. Hence, we reach a contradiction, and
466 algorithm \mathcal{A} does not solve the Collaborative 2-AtomicAppends problem. ◀

5 Crash-prone AtomicAppends with SDLO

468 Theorems 6 and 10 suggest the need to use some external intermediary entity, in order
469 to solve *Competitive AtomicAppends*, even in the absence of crashes, and *Collaborative*
470 *AtomicAppends*, in the case both clients crash, respectively. This is the subject of this section.

5.1 Smart DLO (SDLO)

472 We enhance the MDLO with a special DLO, called *Smart DLO* (SDLO), which is used by
473 the clients to delegate the append of their records to the original MDLO. This SDLO is an
474 extension of a DLO that supports a special “atomic appends” record of the form **[client id,**
475 **{list of involved clients in the atomic append}, record of client]**. When two clients
476 wish to perform an atomic append involving their records and their corresponding DLOs,
477 then they *both* need to append such an atomic appends record in the SDLO; this is like
478 requesting the atomic append service from the SDLO. Once *both* records are appended in the
479 SDLO, then the SDLO appends each record to the corresponding DLO. A pseudocode of this
480 mechanism, together with the client requests, called algorithm \mathcal{A}_{SDLO} is given as Code 3.

Code 3 \mathcal{A}_{SDLO} : SDLO mechanism and requests from client $X \in \{A, B\}$; SDLO code only for atomic appends

```
1: Client  $X$ :  
2:   append( $SDLO, [X, \{X, \bar{X}\}, r_X]$ )  
3:   upon receipt AppendAck from SDLO return  
4: SDLO:  
5:   Init:  $S \leftarrow \emptyset$   
6:   function  $SDLO.append([X, \{X, \bar{X}\}, r_X]$   
7:      $S \leftarrow S \parallel [X, \{X, \bar{X}\}, r_X]$   
8:     if  $[\bar{X}, \{X, \bar{X}\}, r_{\bar{X}}] \in S$  then  
9:       append( $DLO_X, r_X$ )  
10:      append( $DLO_{\bar{X}}, r_{\bar{X}}$ )  
11:     return AppendAck
```

481 So essentially the $SDLO.append$ function in Code 3 can be viewed as a smart contract
482 that “collects” the append requests involved in the AtomicAppends instance and ultimately
483 executes them, by performing individual appends to the corresponding DLOs. Observe that
484 the SDLO does not access the state of DLO_A and DLO_B , but it needs to be able to perform
485 append operations to both of them. In other words, delegation is passed to the SDLO. Also
486 observe that the SDLO returns ack to a client’s request, once their atomic appends request
487 is appended in the SDLO, and not when the actual atomic append takes place.

5.2 Solving AtomicAppends with SDLO

It is not difficult to observe that algorithm \mathcal{A}_{SDLO} can solve the AtomicAppends problem in both utility models, even *in asynchrony*, and even if *both clients crash*. Note that *SDLO*, being a distributed ledger by itself, is reliable despite the fact that some servers implementing it may fail (more below). We show:

► **Theorem 11.** *Algorithm \mathcal{A}_{SDLO} solves both the Collaborative and Competitive 2-AtomicAppends problems in an asynchronous setting, even if both clients may crash.*

Proof. We consider three cases:

1. If no client crashes, then algorithm \mathcal{A}_{SDLO} trivially solves the problem: Both clients invoke the atomic appends request to the SDLO, these operations complete, and the SDLO eventually triggers the two corresponding appends of records r_A and r_B to DLO_A and DLO_B , respectively (both case).
2. At most one client crashes, say client A . Here we have two cases:
 - a. Record $[A, \{A, B\}, r_A]$ is never appended to the SDLO. Since the SDLO will never contain both matching records, it will never append any of the records r_A and r_B (none case).
 - b. Record $[A, \{A, B\}, r_A]$ is appended to the SDLO. Since record $[B, \{A, B\}, r_B]$ will eventually be appended by B in the SDLO, it will proceed with the corresponding appends of records r_A and r_B (both case).
3. Both clients crash. If one of the two clients, say A , crashes before appending $[A, \{A, B\}, r_A]$ to the SDLO, then none of the appends of records r_A and r_B will take place in the corresponding DLOs (none case). However, if both clients crash after they have appended the matching atomic appends records, then both records r_A and r_B will be appended by the SDLO (both case).

Observe that the above hold for both utility models. In Competitive AtomicAppends, if a client does not invoke its atomic append request to the SDLO, it knows that the SDLO will not proceed to append the other client's record. This leaves the clients with their second best utility (see Table 1), and hence, both have incentive to invoke the atomic append requests to the SDLO. The reliability of the SDLO nullifies the uncertainty of the clients, and hence they will follow algorithm \mathcal{A}_{SDLO} . ◀

Observe that algorithm \mathcal{A}_{SDLO} can easily be extended to solve the k -AtomicAppend problem, for any $k \geq 2$, provided that the utility of all records being appended is higher than none being appended for all clients: All clients submit their atomic append request to the SDLO, and then the SDLO performs the corresponding appends. Hence:

► **Corollary 12.** *Both the Collaborative and Competitive k -AtomicAppends problems can be solved with the use of SDLO in the asynchronous setting, even if all k clients may crash.*

Remark: As we discussed in the case 2 of the proof of Theorem 11, if client A crashes and record $[A, \{A, B\}, r_A]$ is never appended to the SDLO, none of the records r_A and r_B will be appended. Now, observe that client B can proceed to perform other operations once it has appended $[B, \{A, B\}, r_B]$ (despite the fact that r_B has not been appended to DLO_B , as it is up to the SDLO to do so). Since clients do not need to wait forever for any operation, algorithm \mathcal{A}_{SDLO} is terminating with respect to the clients. Moreover, the SDLO also terminates the processing of all the operations, as long as the appends in other DLOs terminate.

532 **Implementation issues.** In the above mechanism and theorem, we treat the SDLO as
 533 one entity. Since, however, the SDLO is a distributed ledger implemented by collaborating
 534 servers, there are some low-level implementation details that need to be discussed. If we
 535 assume that the servers implementing the SDLO are prone to only crash faults and that the
 536 SDLO is implemented using an Atomic Broadcast service, as described in [7], then algorithm
 537 \mathcal{A}_{SDLO} can be implemented as follows: Clients A and B submit the atomic append requests
 538 to all servers implementing the SDLO. Once a server appends an atomic append request
 539 record to its local copy of the ledger, it checks if the matching record is already in the ledger.
 540 If this is the case, it issues the two corresponding append operations for records r_A and
 541 r_B . If up to f servers may crash, then it suffices that $f + 1$ servers, in total, perform these
 542 append operations. Given that each record is appended to a DLO at most once (the append
 543 operations are idempotent; if a record is already appended, it will not be appended again), it
 544 follows that both records are appended in the corresponding DLOs.

545 **6 Conclusion**

546 We have introduced the AtomicAppends problem, where given two (or more in general)
 547 clients, each needs to append a record to a corresponding DLO, and do so atomically with
 548 respect to each other: either both records are appended or none. We have considered crash-
 549 prone, rational and risk-averse clients based on two different utility models, *Collaborative*
 550 and *Competitive*, and studied the solvability of the problem under synchrony/asynchrony,
 551 different client append models and failure scenarios. Table 2 gives an overview of our results
 552 (for two clients): if the problem can be solved, then we list the algorithm we developed,
 553 otherwise we use the symbol “ \times ”.

		Synchrony			Asynchrony		
		ND	WD	SDLO	ND	WD	SDLO
Collaborative	<i>no crashes</i>	simple	\mathcal{A}_{DSync}	\mathcal{A}_{SDLO}	simple	$\mathcal{A}_{DAsync}^{(*)}$	\mathcal{A}_{SDLO}
	<i>up to one</i>	\times			\times		
	<i>both</i>	\times	\times				
Competitive	<i>no crashes</i>	\times		\mathcal{A}_{SDLO}	\times		\mathcal{A}_{SDLO}
	<i>up to one</i>						
	<i>both</i>						

(*) might not terminate

■ **Table 2** Overview of the results. ND stands for NoDelegation and WD for WithDelegation.

554 Our results demonstrate a clear separation on the solvability of the problem based on the
 555 utility model assumed when appends are done directly by the clients. When appends are
 556 done using a special type of a DLO, which we call *Smart* DLO (SDLO), then the problem is
 557 solved in both utility models, even in asynchrony and even if both clients may crash.

558 Our investigation of AtomicAppends did not look into the semantics of the records being
 559 appended. Consider, for example, the following scenario. Say that clients A and B initiate
 560 an atomic append request with records r_A and r_B , respectively. While the atomic append
 561 request is being processed, say by the SDLO, client B appends a record r' directly to DLO_B .
 562 It could be the case that the content of record r' is such, that it would affect record r_B . For
 563 example, say that the atomic append involves the exchange of a deed of a car with bitcoins;
 564 record r_A contains the transfer of the deed and r_B the transfer of bitcoins. If r' involves the
 565 withdrawal of bitcoins from the wallet of client B , and this is appended first, then it could
 566 be the case that the wallet no longer contains sufficient bitcoins to carry out the atomic
 567 appends request. Even if we enforce the clients to perform all appends – not only atomic

568 appends – through the SDLO (which practically speaking is not desirable), still we need to
 569 *validate* records. Therefore, to tackle such cases, we will need to consider *validated* DLOs
 570 (VDLOs) [7]. This is a challenging problem, especially in asynchronous settings.

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